

EXTENT OF IMPLEMENTATION OF K TO 12 CURRICULUM IN TOMAS CLAUDIO COLLEGES

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Extent of Implementation of K to 12 Curriculum in Tomas Claudio Colleges

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Abstract

The study attempted to determine the Extent of the Implementation of K to 12 Curriculum in Tomas Claudio Colleges for the school year 2018-2019. The respondents consist of 55 teachers and 334 students. Teachers were described in terms of age, sex, position title educational attainment, length of service and seminars and trainings attended while the students were described in terms of sex, sibling position, number of children in the family, parents' educational attainment and monthly family income. Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn: The teachers and students' role in school are contributory on their views about extent of the implementation of K to 12 curriculum and teachers' personal characteristics have nothing to do with their perception on the extent of the implementation of K to 12 curriculum while for the students most of their Tomas Claudio Colleges Department of Graduates Studies personal characteristics have no bearing on their perception but sex and monthly family income are influential on their differing perception since females are more sensitive on the teaching position and those whose parent earn higher can be able to procure school materials. It was recommended that teachers may be continuous encouraged to pursue advanced education for them to become prepared in facing all the challenges in school. The school may sustain their administrative support focused on teachers, development, instructional materials development and student's development to maintain quality education.

Keywords: *K to 12, Curriculum, DepEd*

Introduction

Education is a vital part of one's individuality. The growth of an individual in the information-based society has pressurized education systems around the world to use technology to teach students the knowledge and skills they need.

The importance of education manifests itself in terms of the need to cultivate the youths of society into matured individuals. Education is important for the youths as youth is their growing stage. It is the time to develop the principles of life, make career decisions, and begin the pursuits of one's goals.

In the education system today, it is what is called the "K to 12 Curriculum". Almost all countries around the world provide twelve years of basic education. Cognizant to this global educational system, the Philippine government changed the old ten-year basic education to 12 years or the K to 12 Program. The Enhanced Basic Education Program is the flagship program of DepEd that desires to offer a curriculum which is attuned to the 21st century.

The modification of curriculum and instruction; standards and assessment; learning environment; human resource management and development; and finance is crucial in operating a school. The effect of such is magnified through the schools', teachers' and learners' performances. While this program is still in its early stage of implementation, comprehensive assessment is necessary to determine the depth and breadth of the program. With the inclusion of several indicators for every area, capsulizing the details to bring out key results, this program is worth evaluating.

Teachers play a vast role in the learning process. In all education systems, the performance of teachers is one of the handfuls of factors determining school effectiveness and learning outcomes. The teacher is a role model who inspires and encourages everyone especially their students to strive for the best and discover their full potential.

The teacher is essential not only in the educational system, but also in the whole wide world. Teachers serve as the molders of young minds and help the students to realize their own personal growth. The researcher believes that an ideal Senior High School teacher should be effective, efficient, and well-disciplined and should carry high morale at all times.

Based on the observations of the researcher, the Tomas Claudio Colleges is in full implementation of K to 12 programs, however there are problems that are needed to address such as teachers' performance. Thus, the researcher opted to conduct this study to know the extent of implementation of K to 12 in Tomas Claudio Colleges specifically teachers' performance.

Research Questions

The study attempted to determine extent of implementation of K to 12 Curriculum in Tomas Claudio Colleges. Specifically, it aimed to answer to the following problems:

1. What are the demographic characteristics of the two groups respondents in terms of;
 - 1.1. Teachers
 - 1.1.1. age;

- 1.1.2. sex;
- 1.1.3. position/title;
- 1.1.4. educational attainment;
- 1.1.5. length of service; and
- 1.1.6. seminars and trainings attended?
- 1.2. Students
 - 1.2.1. sex;
 - 1.2.2. siblings position;
 - 1.2.3. number of children in the family;
 - 1.2.4. parent's educational attainment; and
 - 1.2.5. monthly family income;
2. What is the extent of implementation of K to 12 Curriculum in Tomas Claudio Colleges as perceived by the two group of respondents with respect to:
 - 2.1. teacher factor ;
 - 2.2. school atmosphere;
 - 2.3. student behavior;
 - 2.4. instruction factor; and
 - 2.5. administrative support
3. Is there any significant difference on the extent of implementation of K to 12 Curriculum in Tomas Claudio Colleges as perceived by the two group of respondents with respect to the different aspects?
4. Is there any significant difference on the extent of implementation of K to 12 Curriculum in Tomas Claudio Colleges as perceived by the two group of respondents with respect to the cited aspects in terms of their profile?

Literature Review

High (2012) cited that school readiness in K to 12 includes the readiness of the individual child, the school's readiness for children, and the ability of the family and community to support optimal early child development. It is the responsibility of schools to be ready for all children at all levels of readiness. Children's readiness should become an outcome measure for community-based programs, rather than an exclusion criterion at the beginning of the formal educational experience.

The Abraham and Porio (2011) cited in one of its articles that K to 12 has been met with criticism from youth and student groups, teachers, parents and the academic community. The DepEd, for its part, appears determined to enact the program with its proposed budget catering mostly to preparing the grounds for its eventual implementation. The article also stressed that it is arguably one of the most drastic and controversial programs of the Aquino administration.

In the same article, the DepEd argues that the K-12 program will be the solution to yearly basic education woes and the deteriorating quality of education. Critics, however, counteract that the education crisis needs to be addressed more fundamentally and adding more school years would only exacerbate the situation.

Porter (2008), head of the Curriculum and Learning Management Division of Department of Education in Central Visayas (DepEd-7), said that some elementary and secondary teachers have already underwent divisional, regional and national trainings for the K to 12 programs. The school administrators who have undergone trainings will share their knowledge to fellow teachers in their division.

Villafania (2012) averred that the implementation of K to 12 was also marked with many challenges, particularly in terms of infrastructure as many schools have not yet completed repairs. Educational reform in the Philippines, if we may call it that, is being primarily driven by an effort to meet standards of education in the global world – where our graduates with only ten years of elementary education, no matter the quality of their knowledge through their engineering and nursing degrees, were disadvantaged. That is why both public and private schools in the Philippines, the latter through the leadership of the COCOPEA – already embarked on the K-12 reform, even though this is still in the process of being legislated. The global world with its unforgiving agenda won't let us wait. That is also why there has been much discussion, sometimes passionate debate, about quality assurance.

The government's K-12 program is a much-needed change for the country's education system. Through this program, people may expect better-trained citizens who could be competitive with the knowledge and skills of people trained abroad (Delos Santos, 2012).

On the other hand, Hardy (2010) cited that teachers are one of the key elements in any school and effective teaching is one of the key propellers for school improvement. This review is concerned with how to define a teacher's effectiveness and what makes an effective teacher. It draws out implications for policymakers in education and for improving classroom practice.

Furthermore, the study of Cruz (2010) suggested that in order for schools and universities to cope with new innovations, they should keep at pace with the tempo of societal changes and technological progress. The schools of today should participate in the educational and social revolution. Thus, the curriculum in Philippine schools today has to be geared to the rapid societal changes and the new responsibilities for the new breed of Filipinos.

Methodology

Research Design

Descriptive survey research is the most appropriate for the study since the aim of the investigation is to know the Extent of Implementation of K to 12 Program in Tomas Claudio Colleges. As conferred by Calmorin (2010), Descriptive research supports in decision making process by providing the best solution among available. Descriptive-survey research is appropriate approach wherever the objects of any class vary among themselves, and one is interested in knowing the extent to which different conditions obtain among these objects.

Respondents

The respondents of this study include 100% of the Senior High School Teachers and 334 students at Tomas Claudio Colleges. For teachers, they were described in terms of age, sex, position/title, and educational attainment, length of service and seminars and trainings attended. For students, they will be described in terms of their sex, sibling position, and number of children in the family, parents' educational attainment and monthly family income.

Instrument

A researcher-made questionnaire-checklist was used as the main instrument in gathering the needed data. Part 1 of the questionnaire-checklist dealt on the socio-demographic characteristics of the two groups respondents. For teachers, they were described in terms of age, sex, position/title, and educational attainment, length of service and seminars and trainings attended. For students, they were described in terms of their sex, sibling position, and number of children in the family, parents' educational attainment and monthly family income. Part 2 of the questionnaire-checklist dealt with the questions with regards to the implementation of the Curriculum.

Procedure

The researchers prepared and submitted three proposed titles to the research professor for screening and approval. The title of the study was chosen and approved during the title defense. Right after the approval, the researchers gathered all the necessary data and information needed for the completion of the research proposal. The said research proposal was submitted to the research professor for schedule of the proposal defense.

After the proposal defense, the researchers sought permission to conduct study from the principal of the basic education department of TCC. Construction of research instrument was done and then was validated with the help of the experts in the field of research and education.

Administration and retrieval of the questionnaire-checklist followed. Data gathered were encoded and entered into a matrix to come up with computer-generated results. Analysis and interpretation of the gathered data was done. Editing and revising of the manuscript was accomplished before coming up with the final write up. Summary of findings, conclusions and recommendations were then formulated. After the final defense, revisions were taken and then edited the whole manuscript before bookbinding and submission to the respective offices.

Results and Discussion

This portion presents the results and discussion based on the gathered data.

Profile of the Teacher-Respondents and Student-Respondents

Table 1. *Profile of the Teacher Respondents*

<i>Age</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Rank</i>
31 years old and above	23	41.8	1
26-30 years old	5	9.1	4
21-25 years old	15	27.3	2
18-20 years old	12	21.8	3
Total	55	100.0	
Sex			
Male	19	34.5	2
Female	36	65.5	1
Total	55	100.0	
Position Title			
Coordinator	8	14.5	2
Subject Teacher	47	85.5	1
Total	55	100.0	
Educational Attainment			
With Ph. D. / Ed. D. Units	3	5.5	4
MAEd/MAT Graduate	4	7.3	3

With Maed/MAT Units	6	10.9	2
College Graduate	42	76.4	1
Total	55	100.0	
Length of Service			
11 years and above	3	5.5	3
6-10 years	23	41.8	2
0-2 years	29	52.7	1
Total	55	100.0	
Seminars and Trainings Attended			
International Level	3	5.5	4
National Level	7	12.7	2
Regional Level	4	7.3	3
Division Level	2	3.6	5
District Level	39	70.9	1
Total	55	100.0	

It is reflected in table on the next page that when the teacher respondents are grouped according to age, the 31-year-old and above are on top at 23 or 41.8 percent. This means that teachers are dominated by the oldest groups, however if the number of the young teachers are to be grouped in one, the majority are still young.

It is also depicted on the same table that according to sex the females are at edge at 36 or 65.5 percent against the males at 19 or 34.5 percent, hence showing that teaching profession is indeed a preference of many females.

As to position title, they are dominated by the Subject Teacher having a frequency of 47 or 85.5 percent against the coordinator at 8 or 14.5 percent. This shows that the main role of teachers is instruction, and they are detailed to teach different disciplines.

Meanwhile for educational attainment, the leading group is College Graduate with the highest frequency of 42 or 76.4 percent. This only proves that since teachers are young and mostly fresh graduates, they are just starting to be aware of the relevance of advanced education.

As to their length of service, it is noted that among them, those who have been teaching for 11 years and above obtain the highest frequency of 29 or 52.7 percent. Hence, this indicates that most teachers have spent for more than 6 years in teaching.

Lastly for the seminars and trainings attended, they claim that 39 or 70.9 percent of them attended District level seminars. It shows that their professional growth is not overlooked

It is noted in the next table that when the student respondents are classified according to their age, everybody at 334 or 100 percent belongs to 16-20 years of age. When grouped in terms of sex, the female respondents are more than the males at 177 or 53.0 percent against 157 or 47.0 percent, hence this proves that the population of the senior high school is dominated by the females.

Meanwhile as to sibling position, the first-born respondents lead having the frequency of 87 or 26 percent, followed by the second born, third born, fourth and fifth and above with frequency of 86 or 25.6 percent, 85 or 25.4, 39 or 11.1 percent and 37 or 11.1 percent respectively. As to number of sibling in the family, three children obtains the highest frequency of 86 or 25.7 percent, followed by four children at 78 or 23.4 percent, two children with 73 or 21.9 percent, five children and above at 66 or 19.8 percent and only child with the least frequency of 31 or 9.3 percent, thus this means that there are students who belong to big families.

Table 2. Profile of the Student Respondents

Age	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
16 – 20 years old	334	100.0	1
Total	334	100.0	
Sex			
Male	157	47.0	2
Female	177	53.0	1
Total	334	100.0	
Sibling Position			
First born	87	26.0	1
Second born	86	25.7	2
Third born	85	25.4	3
Fourth born	39	11.7	4
Fifth born and above	37	11.1	5
Total	334	100.0	
Number of Children in the Family			
Only Child	31	9.3	5
Two children	73	21.9	3
Three children	86	25.7	1

Four children	78	23.4	2
Five children and above	66	19.8	4
Total	334	100.0	
Parents Educational Attainment			
Father			
College Graduate	143	42.8	1
College Undergraduate	94	28.1	2
High School Graduate	83	24.9	3
others Specify	14	4.2	4
Total	334	100.0	
Mother			
College Graduate	144	43.1	1
College Undergraduate	125	37.4	2
High School Graduate	49	14.7	3
others Specify	16	4.8	4
Total	334	100.0	
Monthly Family Income			
₱ 20, 000 and above	40	12.0	4
₱ 16, 000 - ₱ 19, 999	74	22.2	3
₱ 11, 000 - ₱ 15, 999	95	28.4	2
₱ 10, 999 and below	125	37.4	1
Total	334	100.0	

When father's educational attainment is considered, it is registered that the College Graduate is on top having a frequency of 143 or 42.8 percent. For the mothers, the same observation is noted since the mothers are dominated by College Graduate at 144 or 43.1 percent.

Lastly, for monthly family income, the respondents who claim that their parents receive P10,999 and below obtains the highest mean of 125 or 37.4 percent, followed by P11,000 – P15,999 with 95 or 28.5 percent, P16,000-P19,999 at 74 or 22.2 percent and finally those who receive monthly earnings of P20,000 and above with a frequency of 40 or 12.0 percent. Hence this is an indication that most of the respondents belong to families who receive low income.

Extent of the Implementation of K to 12 Curriculum in Tomas Claudio Colleges as Perceived by the Two Group of Respondents with Respect to Teacher Factor, School Atmosphere, Student Behavior, Instruction Factor and Administrative Support

Table 3. *Extent of Implementation of K to 12 Curriculum in Tomas Claudio College as Perceived by the Two Group of Respondents with Respect to Teacher Factor*

I ...	Teacher Related Challenges	Teachers		Students	
		wx	VI	wx	VI
1.	have knowledge about the curriculum.	4.20	High Extent	3.46	Moderate Extent
2.	have confidence on the implementation of the curriculum.	3.87	High Extent	3.68	High Extent
3.	have the skills needed and necessary to implement the curriculum.	3.84	High Extent	3.22	Moderate Extent
4.	have trainings and seminars about the curriculum.	3.55	High Extent	3.83	High Extent
5.	fully aware and updated about the new curriculum.	4.05	High Extent	3.68	High Extent
6.	know how to handle Senior High School students.	4.07	High Extent	3.76	High Extent
7.	have a lot of teaching strategies that I can apply in teaching SHS Students.	4.00	High Extent	3.69	High Extent
8.	open for suggestions to my students.	4.55	High Extent	3.70	High Extent
9.	organize in presenting the subject matter and following the course outline.	4.07	High Extent	3.66	High Extent
10.	have mastery on the subject matter I am teaching.	3.91	High Extent	3.75	High Extent
	Composite Mean	4.01	High Extent	3.64	High Extent

The composite means of 4.01 and 3.61 were obtained, hence this means that teachers and students differ in their perception on the challenges faced by the teachers in implementing the K to 12 curriculum. This leads to an implication that although they both feel a high extent of challenges for teachers, the mentors obtain a higher perception because they are the ones who directly experience the needs in their actual teaching like seminars, knowledge and skills, instructional materials and others.

This is in line with the statement of Hemphil as cited by Betonio (2015), a very good teaching performance usually results when one teaches with enthusiasm, competence, effectiveness, and with dedication to the profession. A teacher has to do dual tasks. One is instilling knowledge, and the other one is breaking down the barriers that blocked the process of inculcating such knowledge. The composite means of 3.97 for the teachers and 3.76 for the students are obtained as reflected in the next table. Hence, this indicates that the two groups of respondents that school atmosphere is one of the challenges for teachers.

This implies that teachers and students are agreeable that when classroom atmosphere is distracting, the learning that is about to take

place is also distracted, therefore teaching and learning may have the tendency to be ineffective.

Table 4. *Extent of Implementation of K to 12 Curriculum in Tomas Claudio Colleges as Perceived by the Two Group of Respondents with Respect to School Atmosphere*

<i>School Atmosphere</i>		<i>Teachers</i>		<i>Students</i>	
		<i>wx</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>wx</i>	<i>VI</i>
1.	The school is conducive for learning.	4.04	High Extent	3.66	Moderate Extent
2.	The school has well-ventilated classroom.	4.31	High Extent	3.91	High Extent
3.	The school has well-lighted classroom.	3.85	High Extent	3.48	Moderate Extent
4.	The room has enough chairs and tables	4.16	High Extent	3.95	High Extent
5.	The school is free from noise that may distract the classes.	3.95	High Extent	3.75	High Extent
6.	The school is safe.	3.93	High Extent	3.80	High Extent
7.	The room is spacious enough for classroom activities.	3.93	High Extent	3.78	High Extent
8.	The room is free from bad odor or smell coming from the outside.	3.85	High Extent	3.88	High Extent
9.	The room has clean and sturdy whiteboard.	3.78	High Extent	3.69	High Extent
10.	The room provides comfort ability to the students and teachers.	3.89	High Extent	3.82	High Extent
Composite Mean		3.97	High Extent	3.76	High Extent

This implies that teachers and students are agreeable that when classroom atmosphere is distracting, the learning that is about to take place is also distracted, therefore teaching and learning may have the tendency to be ineffective. This can be associated with an article published at Philippine Basic Education blog spot entitled "A Teacher's Engagement Inside the Classroom" (2010), that the first factor is the class size (pupils to teacher ratio) and does not have a measurable impact on a teacher's engagement. There is a fixed cost for every class on a teacher's engagement, which does not depend on the number of students. School conditions like availability of resources.

Table 5. *Extent of Implementation of K to 12 Curriculum in Tomas Claudio Colleges as Perceived by the Two Group of Respondents with Respect to Student Behavior*

<i>Student Behavior</i>		<i>Teachers</i>		<i>Students</i>	
		<i>wx</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>wx</i>	<i>VI</i>
1.	are very eager to learn.	3.60	High Extent	3.58	Moderate Extent
2.	listen attentively in the discussion.	3.73	High Extent	3.77	High Extent
3.	attention span of the students is good.	3.22	Moderate Extent	3.34	Moderate Extent
4.	participate well in the class.	3.87	High Extent	3.86	High Extent
5.	are sociable.	3.78	High Extent	3.70	High Extent
6.	can easily catch up with the lesson	3.85	High Extent	3.75	High Extent
7.	has low level of motivation	3.55	High Extent	3.63	High Extent
8.	always want to have a performance activity rather than lecture.	3.84	High Extent	3.77	High Extent
9.	are disciplined and manageable.	3.69	High Extent	3.67	High Extent
10.	easily understand the lesson.	3.62	High Extent	3.76	High Extent
Composite Mean		3.67	High Extent	3.68	High Extent

The composite means of 3.67 for teachers and 3.68 a bit higher for the students explains that student's perception is truly positive because this aspect concerns them. From this result it can be implied that teachers and students are both sensible that students' participation is challenging because this is of the proofs that the student obtains cognition of lessons discussed by the teachers. This is in line with the statement of Dinham & Scott (2008) who presume that commitment was supposed to be a normal component of teaching from the very start. They highlighted the necessity for quality teacher education in relation to competency-based and commitment-oriented teacher education. If teachers purchase professional competencies and commitment, it will result in sound teacher performance.

Table 6. *Extent of Implementation of K to 12 Curriculum in Tomas Claudio Colleges as Perceived by the Two Group of Respondents with Respect to Instruction Factor*

<i>Curriculum Related Challenges</i>		<i>Teachers</i>		<i>Students</i>	
		<i>wx</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>wx</i>	<i>VI</i>
1.	The curriculum is easy to understand.	3.73	High Extent	3.58	High Extent
2.	The scope of curriculum is enough and sufficient.	3.98	High Extent	3.85	High Extent
3.	The curriculum gives enough time for students to digest.	3.73	High Extent	3.32	Moderate Extent
4.	I use chalk and board in explaining the lesson.	4.00	High Extent	3.88	High Extent
5.	maximize the workbook/ learning material in teaching.	3.80	High Extent	3.64	High Extent
6.	I use varied references in teaching the lesson.	3.80	High Extent	3.75	High Extent
7.	I use PowerPoint presentation in teacher.	3.69	High Extent	3.68	High Extent
8.	I use realia/real objects in teaching.	3.71	High Extent	3.67	High Extent
9.	I prefer hands-on experience in teaching.	3.78	High Extent	3.68	High Extent
10.	I maximize social media as form of instruction.	3.85	High Extent	3.79	High Extent
Composite Mean		3.81	High Extent	3.68	High Extent

The composite means of 3.81 for teachers and 3.68 for students are obtained. This leads to an implication that instruction factors as challenges are more observed and experienced by the teachers because they are the ones concerned in the preparation of instructional materials while the students just follow the flow the teachers present for them.

This has congruency on the statement of Griffin (2008) focuses on the situation within the teaching profession. She argues that for many teachers, the last 20 years have been years of survival, rather than development.

The composite means of 3.74 for teachers and 3.67 for students in the next table reflect their different perceptions because administration’s support is seen only by the students based on the materials provided to them through classroom and instructional materials, but they do not actually observe the provisions given by the administration to teachers’ professional growth.

Table 7. *Extent of Implementation of K to 12 Curriculum in Tomas Claudio Colleges as Perceived by the Two Group of Respondents with Respect to Administrative Support*

	<i>Administrative Support</i>	<i>Teachers</i>		<i>Students</i>	
		<i>wx</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>wx</i>	<i>VI</i>
1.	The school provides enough and sufficient learning materials.	3.71	High Extent	3.61	High Extent
2.	The school provides training and seminars.	3.67	High Extent	3.85	High Extent
3.	The school provides computer-assisted resources.	3.18	Moderate Extent	3.37	Moderate Extent
4.	The school reduces non-teaching duties.	3.84	High Extent	3.89	High Extent
5.	The school is open for suggestions.	3.69	High Extent	3.67	High Extent
6.	The school provides assistance in professional growth.	4.09	High Extent	3.75	High Extent
7.	The school gives funds for research works.	3.69	High Extent	3.70	High Extent
8.	The school supports the activities undertaken by teacher.	3.87	High Extent	3.67	High Extent
9.	The school finances school-related activities of teachers.	3.80	High Extent	3.69	High Extent
10.	The school encourages teachers to enroll post graduate studies.	3.89	High Extent	3.82	High Extent
	Composite Mean	3.74	High Extent	3.67	High Extent

This finding implies that one’ role in school makes him understand the support provided to the stakeholders, that include students, teachers, parents and others. This further implies that the administration is trying its best to provide assistance in various form to attain quality teaching.

This is in consonance with the explanation of Harriss (2008) who appeals that eventually, the performance of teachers affects the performance of their students. His research investigates the bond of the performance of teachers and the leadership practices that they have used. The author was encouraged to embark on his study ever since he was in hunt of techniques to develop how his performance can turn out to be fine.

Significant Difference on the Extent of Implementation of K to 12 Curriculum in Tomas Claudio Colleges with Respect to the Different Aspects

Table 8. *Result of the t-test in the Significant Difference Between the Perception of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Extent of Challenges Faced by Senior High School Teachers in the Implementation of K to 12 Curriculum with Respect to the Different Aspects*

<i>Group</i>	<i>Test</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>t-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
Teacher Factor	Students	334	3.638	0.545	-4.707	.000	Reject Ho	Significant
	Teachers	55	4.011	0.537				
School Atmosphere	Students	334	3.764	0.620	-2.293	.022	Reject Ho	Significant
	Teachers	55	3.969	0.590				
Student Behavior	Students	285	3.684	0.556	.119	.905	Accept Ho	Not Significant
	Teachers	55	3.675	0.535				
Instruction Factor	Students	334	3.681	0.541	-1.604	.110	Accept Ho	Not Significant
	Teachers	55	3.807	0.531				
Administrative Support	Students	334	3.671	0.543	-.900	.368	Accept Ho	Not Significant
	Teachers	55	3.744	0.629				

It is revealed in table 10 that the hypothesis is accepted in terms of students’ behavior, instruction factor, and administrative support since the p-values of .905, 110 and .368 all exceeded the f-values of .119, -1.604 and -.900 but it is rejected in terms teacher factor and school atmosphere since the computed p-values of .000 and .022 are less than -4.707 and -2.293, therefore there is no significant difference on the perception of the two groups of respondents with respect to students’ behavior, instruction factor, and administrative support but there is significant difference with respect to teacher factor and school atmosphere.

This leads to an implication that teachers and students’ role in school are contributory on their views of the challenges faced by the teachers. Limited understanding of the students on the needs of professional development, teachers’ preparation and skills makes them give limited perception also.

This is related to the findings of Porter (2008) probes the relationship between primary school teachers' self-reported and actual use of classroom management strategies.

Significant Difference on the Extent of Implementation of K to 12 Curriculum in Tomas Claudio Colleges as Perceived by the Two Groups Respondents with Respect to the Cited Aspects in Terms of their Profile

Table 9. *Significant Difference Between the Perception of the Teacher Respondents on the Extent of Challenges Faced by Senior High School Teachers in the Implementation of K to 12 Curriculum with Respect to the Cited Aspects in Terms of their Profile*

Aspect	F-value	p-value	Decision	Verbal Interpretation
Age				
Teacher Factor	2.299	0.088	Accept Ho	Not Significant
School Atmosphere	0.516	0.673	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Student Behavior	0.201	0.896	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Instruction Factor	0.672	0.573	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Administrative Support	1.179	0.327	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Sex				
Teacher Factor	3.139	0.082	Accept Ho	Not Significant
School Atmosphere	0.010	0.920	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Student Behavior	0.997	0.322	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Instruction Factor	0.449	0.506	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Administrative Support	0.603	0.441	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Position Title				
Teacher Factor	1.500	0.226	Accept Ho	Not Significant
School Atmosphere	0.083	0.775	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Student Behavior	2.302	0.135	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Instruction Factor	0.002	0.967	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Administrative Support	0.154	0.696	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Educational Attainment				
Teacher Factor	0.635	0.596	Accept Ho	Not Significant
School Atmosphere	2.242	0.095	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Student Behavior	2.533	0.067	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Instruction Factor	1.309	0.282	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Administrative Support	1.098	0.359	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Length of Service				
Teacher Factor	0.401	0.672	Accept Ho	Not Significant
School Atmosphere	0.345	0.710	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Student Behavior	0.585	0.561	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Instruction Factor	0.152	0.859	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Administrative Support	0.392	0.678	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Seminars and Trainings Attended				
Teacher Factor	1.434	0.236	Accept Ho	Not Significant
School Atmosphere	0.104	0.980	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Student Behavior	2.095	0.095	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Instruction Factor	1.385	0.252	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Administrative Support	0.602	0.663	Accept Ho	Not Significant

The hypothesis on the teacher's perception on the extent of challenges is accepted in terms of age, sex, position title, educational attainment, length of service and seminars and trainings attended across all aspects since all the p- values are found higher than 0.05 level of significance, therefore there is no significant difference on the teacher's perception of the challenges they face in terms of their profile.

This leads to an implication that regardless of personal characteristics, teachers' views of the challenges they face in school are alike since they believe that all these being part and parcel of effective teaching are relevant and are needed to be given attention all the time.

This is congruent to the findings of Silver (2009), the Journal of Business and Management Studies (2015) states that quality classroom instruction largely depends on quality teachers, schools, and learners.

The table 10 reflects that the hypothesis on the student's perception of the challenges faced by the teachers is accepted in terms of sibling position, number of sibling in the family and parents' educational attainment is accepted since all the computed p-values are higher than the f-values at 0.05 level of significance. It is likewise accepted in terms of sex and monthly family income across school atmosphere, students' behavior, instruction factor and administrative support since all the p-values of these aspects also exceeded the 0.05 level of significance, yet it is rejected in terms of sex and monthly family income and teacher factor since the computed F-values at 3.013 and 2.638 are associated with p-values of 0.030 and .034, therefore there is no significant difference in terms of sibling position, number of sibling in the family, parents educational attainment but there is significant difference in terms of sex and monthly family

income.

Table 10. *Significant Difference on the Extent of Implementation of K to 12 Curriculum in Tomas Claudio Colleges as Perceived by the Two Groups Respondents with Respect to the Cited Aspects in Terms of their Profile*

Aspect	F-value	p-value	Decision	Verbal Interpretation
Sex				
Teacher Factor	3.013	0.030	Reject Ho	Significant
School Atmosphere	1.584	0.193	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Student Behavior	1.391	0.246	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Instruction Factor	1.233	0.298	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Administrative Support	1.148	0.330	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Sibling Position				
Teacher Factor	1.379	0.241	Accept Ho	Not Significant
School Atmosphere	1.386	0.238	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Student Behavior	0.157	0.960	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Instruction Factor	0.503	0.733	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Administrative Support	0.221	0.927	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Number of Children in the Family				
Teacher Factor	0.521	0.761	Accept Ho	Not Significant
School Atmosphere	0.945	0.452	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Student Behavior	0.484	0.788	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Instruction Factor	0.666	0.649	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Administrative Support	0.787	0.560	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Parents Educational Attainment				
Father				
Teacher Factor	0.594	0.619	Accept Ho	Not Significant
School Atmosphere	0.023	0.995	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Student Behavior	0.109	0.955	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Instruction Factor	0.651	0.583	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Administrative Support	1.760	0.155	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Mother				
Teacher Factor	0.570	0.685	Accept Ho	Not Significant
School Atmosphere	2.175	0.072	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Student Behavior	0.354	0.841	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Instruction Factor	1.325	0.260	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Administrative Support	0.843	0.499	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Monthly Family Income				
Teacher Factor	2.638	0.034	Reject Ho	Significant
School Atmosphere	1.012	0.401	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Student Behavior	0.909	0.459	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Instruction Factor	0.439	0.780	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Administrative Support	3.960	0.004	Accept Ho	Not Significant

This implies that most of the personal characteristics of the students have no bearing on their perception, but sex and monthly family income are influential on their differing perception since females are more sensitive on the teaching position and those whose parent earn higher can be able to procure school materials that can be used in teaching and learning activities.

This is in conformity with the study of Tabora (2012), that the level of stresses experienced by the faculty reveals that in general, the level of stresses as experienced by the faculty is still manageable as supported by the rating of 2.48 with verbal description of low.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

The teachers and students' role in school are contributory on their views of the extent of implementation of K to 12 Curriculum

Teachers' personal characteristics have nothing to do with their perception about Extent of Implementation of K to 12 Curriculum while for the students most of their personal characteristics have no bearing on their perception, but sex and monthly family income are influential on their differing perception since females are more sensitive on the teaching position and those whose parent earn higher can be able to procure school materials

References

- Abraham, F. and Porio, C. (2011) "The DepEd's Arguments on the Implementation of K to 12", Philippine Online Chronicles.
- Calmorin, L. (2010). "Methods of Research and Thesis Writing, Manila: Rex Book Store.

- Cruz, I. (2010). "Implementation of K to 12, Mini Critique." *The Philippine Star*. (Retrieved May 2013 from: <http://www.philstar.com>.)
- Delos Santos, E. (2012) "K to 12 Program in the Philippines." Retrieved May 2013 from: <http://studymode.com>.
- Dinham and Scott (2008). "Correcting the course of math education", *Principal Leadership*, 7(5), 27-31.
- Griffin, L. (2008). "Varieties of constructivism: Their metaphors, epistemologies and pedagogical implications." *Hiroshima Journal of Mathematics Education*, 2, 1-14.
- Hardy, I. (2010). "Critiquing Teacher Professional Development: Teacher Learning within the Field of Teachers' Work, *Critical Studies in Education*, 51(1), 71-84.
- Harris, J. (2008). "Metaphors and models in translation between College and workplace mathematics." *Educational Studies in Mathematics*. 64(3), 345-371.
- Porter, J. (2008). "Economic perspectives on investments in teacher quality: Lessons learned from research on productivity and human resource development." Retrieved 2013 from: www.epaa.asu.edu/epaa/v8n33.html.
- Silver, E. A., Mesa, V. M., Morris, K. A., Star, J. R., & Benken, B. M. (2009). "Teaching mathematics for understanding: An analysis of lessons submitted by teachers seeking NBPTS certification", *American Educational Research Journal*, To Retrieved from <http://aeri.aera.net>, DOI: 10.3102/0002831208326559.
- Tabora, J. (2012) "Challenges in Implementing K-12 and Transformative Education." Retrieved 2013 from: <http://taboras.wordpress.com>.
- Villafania, A. (2012) "The Implementation of the K+12 Program." Retrieved May 2013 from: <http://loqal.ph>.

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